

HEMATOLOGICAL INDICATORS OF THE USE OF UNICELLULAR GREEN ALGAE IN CATTLE

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Abstract. *This article describes the research conducted on feeding cattle on the basis of unicellular blue-green algae, the use of these algae in cattle breeding, and the morphological and biochemical parameters of cattle blood, and the content of erythrocytes, leukocytes and hemoglobin in the blood. The article studies the content of erythrocytes, leukocytes and hemoglobin in the blood of cattle fed with a suspension of unicellular blue-green algae and porridge prepared with coarse plant extract. The achievements achieved as a result of studying blood composition, the importance of increasing the economic efficiency of the farm and creating additional jobs, taking into account the reduced use of veterinary drugs and the reduction of veterinary services by 25-30%, as well as the advantages of the unicellular blue-green algae chlorella, are discussed.*

Keywords: *chlorella, unicellular, green, algae, cattle, blood analysis, erythrocytes, leukocytes, hemoglobin, nutrition, research, milk production, farm, economic efficiency, jobs and veterinary services.*

Relevance of the Topic. Livestock farming plays a crucial role in ensuring food security for the population. In this context, the President and the Government of our Republic are placing significant emphasis on the development of this vital sector.

A clear example of this is the adoption by the President of three Resolutions in the first five months of 2019: Resolution No. PQ-4243 dated March 16, 2019, “On Measures for the Further Development and Support of the Livestock Sector”; Resolution No. PQ-4254 dated March 28, 2019, “On the Organization of the Activities of the State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the Development of Veterinary Medicine and Livestock”; and Law No. O‘RQ-538 dated May 20, 2019, “On Pastures.”

These Law and Resolutions are aimed at encouraging an increase in livestock numbers in personal subsidiary plots, dehkan (smallholder) farms, and farmer enterprises, as well as boosting the volume of livestock product output. They play an important role in the development of this sector.

There are sufficient opportunities in our Republic for the further development of livestock farming. In this regard, the main task of institutions working in various areas of livestock production, as well as the researchers involved, is to ensure the productivity of farm animals, provide them with balanced nutrition, increase the volume and improve the quality of livestock products, prevent and treat infectious and non-infectious diseases, and to develop the scientific foundations and effective methods for creating high-yielding varieties and hybrids of forage crops.

Chlorella is a highly effective and beneficial feed for cattle. It is an environmentally clean, biologically safe, and inexpensive feed. It is rich in nutrients such as proteins, amino acids,

vitamins, and minerals. Chlorella is a very nutritious feed source for livestock, especially cattle, as it contains a range of essential nutrients including proteins, vitamins, minerals, and important fatty acids. This composition supports the growth of animals and helps maintain their overall health.

Purpose and Methods of the Study. In assessing the metabolic processes and nutritional value of feeding in cattle, the study of hematological parameters of their blood is of great importance. Table 4.3.1 presents the changes in the morphological parameters of cattle blood composition in the experimental groups given a suspension of unicellular green algae.

Table 1

Morphological parameters of the blood of cattle fed with a suspension of unicellular green algae

Groups	Indicators					
	Erythrocytes, million/mm ³		Leukocytes, million/mm ³		Hemoglobin, g/%	
	$\bar{X} \pm S\bar{x}$	Cv,%	$\bar{X} \pm S\bar{x}$	Cv,%	$\bar{X} \pm S\bar{x}$	Cv,%
Control	5,92±0,6	12,31	8,4±0,51	6,47	11,8±2,76	6,82
First experiment	7,22±0,6	8,36	7,91±0,36	4,73	12,9±0,24	1,56
Second experiment	6,84±0,7	10,29	7,56±0,32	6,81	12,2±0,14	3,57

As seen in Table 1, changes were observed in the amounts of erythrocytes, leukocytes, and hemoglobin in the blood of cattle in the experimental groups. For example, the erythrocyte count in the blood of the control group cattle was 22.0% and 15.2% lower compared to the experimental groups I and II, respectively; the leukocyte count was 43.1% and 34.3% higher, respectively; and hemoglobin was 18.4% and 11.4% lower.

Table 2

Biochemical parameters of the blood of cattle fed with a suspension of unicellular green algae

Groups	Indicators					
	Erythrocytes, million/mm ³		Leukocytes, million/mm ³		Hemoglobin, g/%	
	$\bar{X} \pm S\bar{x}$	Cv,%	$\bar{X} \pm S\bar{x}$	Cv,%	$\bar{X} \pm S\bar{x}$	Cv,%
Control	5,87±0,8	13,51	9,94±0,59	6,02	11,1±0,54	5,03
First experiment	7,18±0,6	8,32	5,76±0,24	4,79	13,3±0,18	1,46
Second experiment	6,7±0,6	10,24	6,6±0,41	6,49	12,5±0,39	3,59

As seen in Table 2, changes were observed in the amounts of erythrocytes, leukocytes, and hemoglobin in the blood of cattle fed with a suspension of unicellular green algae. For example, the erythrocyte count in the blood of the control group cattle was 22.0% and 15.2% lower

compared to the experimental groups I and II, respectively; the leukocyte count was 43.1% and 34.3% higher, respectively; and hemoglobin was 18.4% and 11.4% lower.

No significant differences were observed between the groups in terms of the morphological indicators in the blood, which indicates that regardless of the type of feed, the metabolic processes in all groups proceeded at nearly the same level.

Table 3 presents the morphological indicators in the blood of cattle fed with a suspension of unicellular green algae and porridge prepared using plant flour.

Table 3

Morphological indicators of the blood of cattle fed with a "mixed feed" prepared using a suspension of unicellular green algae and plant flour, $\bar{X} \pm S\bar{x}$

Indicators	Groups (n=5)		
	Control	First experiment	First experiment
At the beginning of the experiment			
Carotene, mg%	0,258±0,07	0,298±0,02	0,279±0,06
Total protein, g%	7,38±0,21	7,72±0,26	7,65±0,19
Calcium, mmol%	3,49±0,11	3,52±0,14	3,50±0,16
Phosphorus, mmol%	2,45±0,06	2,55±0,24	2,49±0,26
At the end of the experiment			
Carotene, mg%	0,261±0,02	0,383±0,01	0,319±0,01
Total protein, g%	7,47±0,12	7,86±0,09	7,71±0,11
Calcium, mmol%	3,51±0,17	3,59±0,16	3,52±0,14
Phosphorus, mmol%	2,59±0,12	2,65±0,21	2,62±0,08

The table data shows that by the end of the experiment, the morphological blood indicators of the cattle increased compared to the beginning of the experiment, with a significant rise in the levels of substances such as total protein, calcium, phosphorus, and carotene. It is important to note that the levels of total protein, calcium, phosphorus, and carotene in the blood serum of the cattle in the experimental groups were somewhat higher compared to the control group. For example, in the cattle of the first experimental group, the total protein content in the blood was 5.22% higher, calcium 2.27% higher, phosphorus 2.31% higher, and carotene 15.4% higher than in the control group. Similarly, in the second experimental group, the total protein content was 3.21% higher, calcium 0.28% higher, phosphorus 1.15% higher, and carotene 4.36% higher compared to the control group.

Analyzing the data in Table 4, the following results were obtained: in the cattle fed with a "mixed feed" prepared using a suspension of unicellular green algae and plant flour, the biochemical blood indicators were as follows. In the serum of animals from the experimental groups, the levels of total protein, calcium, phosphorus, and carotene were slightly higher compared to the control group. For example, in the blood of cattle from the first experimental group, total protein was 3.61% higher, calcium — 1.42% higher, and phosphorus — 1.54% higher compared to the control group. Similarly, in the second experimental group, total protein was 2.4% higher, no significant difference was observed in calcium levels, phosphorus was 1.1% higher, and carotene was 2.9% higher than in the control group.

Table 4

Biochemical indicators of the blood of cattle fed with a “mixed feed” prepared using a suspension of unicellular green algae and plant flour, $\bar{X} \pm S\bar{x}$

Indicators	Groups (h=5)		
	Control	First experiment	First experiment
At the beginning of the experiment			
Carotene, mg%	0,258±0,07	0,284±0,02	0,275±0,06
Total protein, g%	7,38±0,21	7,69±0,26	7,61±0,19
Calcium, mmol%	3,49±0,11	3,51±0,14	3,50±0,24
Phosphorus, mmol%	2,45±0,06	2,53±0,28	2,50±0,29
At the end of the experiment			
Carotene, mg%	0,261±0,02	0,371±0,01	0,309±0,01
Total protein, g%	7,47±0,12	7,74±0,09	7,65±0,11
Calcium, mmol%	3,51±0,17	3,56±0,16	3,51±0,28
Phosphorus, mmol%	2,59±0,12	2,63±0,24	2,61±0,28

Conclusion

1. In all groups, the coefficient of variation for the studied indicators was similar and showed sufficiently high values, indicating that the physiological parameters of the cattle in the groups remained within the normal range.

2. The results of the conducted studies showed that regardless of the type of feeding, the morphological and biochemical indicators of the cattle's blood remained within physiological norms.

3. Animals in all groups demonstrated a high level of saturation of elements in the morphological and biochemical composition of the blood.

4. The consumption of feeds rich in nutrients, proteins, vitamins, and amino acids by the cattle contributed to the active functioning of metabolic processes in their bodies.

5. Thus, the use of suspensions of unicellular green and blue-green algae, as well as porridge prepared with the addition of coarse plant meal, in cattle feeding produces positive results.

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